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PERCEPTION AND ITS PATHOLOGIES

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Abstract: *Three articles provide information on the fact that the perception of things and events depends on the individuality of each person.*

Key words: *Perception, events, sensory organs, Person, human, psychology, attention, memory, thinking, imagination, feeling and will.*

A person perceives and perceives events in the environment throughout his life. These two concepts are so closely related that it is difficult to understand them separately. We perceive events with the help of our senses, and it is on the basis of these sensations that perception is formed. Intuition reflects some features of things and events in the environment around us, and perception organizes them, shows them in our mind and creates a whole image. Perception is a process of knowing, and it is a complex process compared to intuition. As a person matures, the ability to perceive improves with development.

When a new baby is born, it senses the world, but it cannot perceive it. This process will develop in them later.

The concept of perception is defined differently by different scientists from their point of view. For example, in E. Goziyev's "General Psychology" textbook, "Because

perception is considered a complex and meaningful mental process compared to sensations, all mental states, events, features are properties and the overall content of the human mind, acquired knowledge, experiences, skills are manifested in one period, participate in reflection.

In M.Vahidov's textbook "Psychology" it is mentioned that "perception is the reflection of things and events affecting our sense organs as a whole".

In the textbook "Psychology" by V. Karimova, "Perception is such a form of our knowledge that it provides us with a holistic reflection of the object we need at the same time with its properties and characteristics among many different objects and events in existence." it is said.

Based on the above thoughts, perception is defined as follows: Perception means that the images of events are reflected in a person's mind as a whole, which directly affects the senses.

The perception of things and events depends on the individuality of each person. Because two people may not perceive the same event in the same way. For example, if someone likens a cloud in the sky to different things, for someone else, it may mean nothing but a simple cloud.

Despite the fact that almost all our senses participate in the process of perception, we cannot say that perception consists of a simple sum of our senses. Because in addition to intuition, the experience that a person has gained up to this time is also involved. That is, we know what an object we have seen before and easily perceive it. We have a hard time understanding what we don't see at all.

Attention, memory, thinking, imagination, emotion and will are also involved in the process of perception. In addition, imagination is also important in the process of perception. Z. Ibodullayev stated in the textbook "Medical Psychology" that "reviving, i.e. restoring, previously perceived images in our mind is called "Imagination".

We can say about the participation of the imagination in perception that in the process of perception, a person adds something from himself and expands the content

of the image formed from what he perceives. This process is clearly seen in children. For example: a little girl can imagine her doll as a baby and call it "Alla".

The participation of emotions in perception is reflected in relationships. For example: to a person who is scared in the dark at night, an ordinary duck looks like a person who is lying in wait. And on the contrary, if a person is in a good mood, everything can seem beautiful to him.

The importance of intuition in perception is that every sense organ has the most important place. That is, we can say that we can see a picture while perceiving, see the interlocutor while perceiving his thoughts, hear the interlocutor while perceiving his thoughts, taste while evaluating food, smell while perceiving a perfume, and so on.

Attention is also important in perception, so that only when we pay attention to things and events, we perceive them clearly.

A person perceives based on his previous experience, and this process is related to memory.

We clarify the content of our perception by naming things.

Thinking becomes active when we perceive something that we have not seen before. Thinking is also an important process, and perception is also slow in a mentally retarded person.

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